

Automated Digital Twins for Circular Value Chains: A Data-Driven Process Mining Approach

13 partners

7 countries

7.2M Total Budget

36 Months

auto-twin-project.eu

Automatically
Generated &
Autonomous
Digital Twins

A trustworthy
high-resolution
track & trace
of products
and processes

Reduce skills
and knowledge
gaps

AI algorithms
for decision
making
at Green
Gateways

The Project

AUTO-TWIN is a new method for creating digital twins, which are digital replicas of physical systems. It aims to address the limitations of current system engineering models by introducing a breakthrough method for automated process-aware discovery towards autonomous Digital Twins generation. This is done by adopting an

International Data Space (IDS)-based common data space, which enables the automated process of creating digital twins, thus making it more efficient and cost-effective. Additionally, AUTO-TWIN integrates novel hardware technologies into the digital thread, which is a key component of creating digital twins, to create smart Green Gateways.

Battery Cloud Platform | State-of-Health

focuses on monitoring the performance of the car battery, including its overall health, in real-time through the cloud platform. This data will be used to optimize the refurbishment process of the battery when it is brought back to the Libattion facility.

PET Endless Recycling

focuses on the automated digitalization of the recycling process chain. The data collected from these processes will be used to generate and operate a digital twin able to identify systems improvement actions in terms of efficiency and sustainability.

Sterilization Process | Health Sector

focuses on the sterilization process in hospitals. The data collected from the process will help to optimize items flow, costs, and deliveries thanks to decisions supported by digital twin.

Use Cases

Consortium

Italy

Greece

Spain

Turkey

KOÇ ÜNİVERSİTESİ

Lithuania

Netherlands

Switzerland

Israel

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